

RESUME SORTING USING MACHINE LEARNING: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Hiring is a crucial process in the recruitment organizations. Recruitment industry, with the rapid automation of hiring process has grown tremendously. Candidates are able to upload their resumes in diverse formats on variety of job portals. Resume sorting using varied machine learning techniques for improving this process is a great tool for ranking and evaluating the resumes; in order to choose the best skilled person from the pool of resumes. With the automation of resume sorting systems, different web based applications as well as varied recruiting agencies utilize Machine Learning and NLP techniques for this purpose. It also helps with customized shortlisting of the candidates. This paper presents a comprehensive review of various resumes sorting techniques using machine learning with key benefits like optimal performance, better accuracy, reduce cost, feature extraction, classification and ranking of resumes.

Keywords: Deep Learning, Resume Screening, Natural Language Processing, Classification, Ranking, Hiring Process, Automation, Machine Learning.

INTRODUCTION

If a recruiter cannot organize the large number of applications, it is difficult to select the best candidate for the job. The significance of efficient and effective resume sorting is at the pacemaker of any HR policies. The manual process of sorting and screening the resumes is judgmental and unsustainable task. Conventional based methods depend upon recruiters manually screening each resumes, where there's great chances of biasing and unskillfulness. Managing such huge bulk of resumes is a tedious and time consuming process as the agencies provide numerous jobs at a time and storing them physically is hard.

Machine Learning provides a path through which machines can be trained to work out as per instructions provided and make human life easier. Models in Machine Learning rely on prior outcomes, so they are able to interpret correct and correct choices.

The rapid growth of automation industry provides a chance to the skilled persons who might have lost the chance of job in their manual recruitment process and thereby eliminating the unworthy candidate. As it's a matter of great deal to bind with the procedural process of hiring the skilled ones and to treat them with dignity. Deep Learning, a subfield of Machine Learning have shown propounding success in various NLP tasks such as text classification, feature extraction and sequence modelling. Deep learning enables to automatically grasp complex features from raw unstructured data, thereby proving itself a promising solution in automating and optimizing resume sorting. This paper reviews the existing literature on the

application of machine learning for resume sorting. We aim to provide a comprehensive overview of the different machine learning architectures used.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Lokesh. S et al., (2022) [1] proposed to use NLP methods to help spot key information in the resumes to make hiring easier. The model learns to assess if a candidate's qualifications, background and other traits are appropriate for the open position. Used as resume screener are three machine learning classifiers: Logistic Classifier, Support Vector Classifier and Decision Tree.

Riya Pal et al., (2022) [2] stated that, using Machine Learning, the text analysis of resumes will be carried out using Nave Bayes, Random Forest and SVM, helping to sort information about skills and categorize them within particular job profiles.

Aakankshu Rawat et al., (2021) [3] suggested looking into several different Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) techniques to address difficulties in hiring. Most focus has been placed on "Resume/CV Parsing" to improve the speed of hiring.

Dipti Suhas Chavare et al., (2023) [4] reported that résumés are screened automatically by software through advanced Natural Language. The recruiters use the model to review and sort resumes as described in the job openings in no time. It allows you to hire more easily since the Spacy NER model automatically detects needed entities from resume documents.

Chirag Daryania et al., (2020) [5] proposed an Automated Resume Screening System that used Natural Language Processing and Similarity Vector Space Model to link each resume to the job description and advised using a vectorisation model along with cosine similarity. On the basis of this data, they will work out rankings to assist in selecting the best person for the position.

Momin Adnan et al., (2016) [6] proposed a system for screening candidates for recruitment using Linear SVM classifier. The model used cosine similarity, KNN and content-based Recommendation so as to search for the resumes that lies closest to the specified description of the job. The model only accepts CVs in CSV format, while most CVs are in.doc, .pdf, and other formats. Because "gensim" summarises the text, there is a risk that key pieces of information could be missed in the summary.

Soumia CHAFI et al. (2023) [7] recommended a novel way to classify CVs in a distributed system by matching them with job postings and using BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers), a pre-trained language model.

Riza Tanaz Fareed et al., (2021) [8] suggested a machine learning system that can select appropriate resumes for HR using the job description given. The first thing in the methodology was to sort resumes into several groups by similarity. It also suggests resumes that are similar to the job description. KNN Algorithm sorts resumes into groups and Cosine Similarity measures how similar each resume is to the job description; candidates are ranked accordingly. We build a resume parser which extracts complete information from candidate resumes. This parser is made available to the public in the form of a web application. Second, we use BERT sentence pair classification to perform ranking based on their suitability to the job description

Irfan Ali et al., (2022) [9] this experimental study, a machine learning and natural language processing (NLP) RCS has been developed to automatically group Resumes by job category, including performance guarantees. The outcomes of the study include an evaluation of different ML algorithms and NLP methods which led to a proposed solution that is more

accurate and reliable in all situations. The features were tested on various ML classifiers, in particular SVM (Linear, SGD, SVC and NuSVC), Naïve Bayes (Bernoulli, Multinomial & Gaussian), K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) and Logistic Regression (LR).

Gopalakrishna S.T. et al., (2022) [10] the study was intended to assign the suitable project to recruiters. The research study applied Named Entity Recognition (NER) together with Logistic Regression and K-Nearest Neighbours for detection.

Bhoir et al., (2023) [16] investigated video resume parsing by using visual and audio processing techniques. The results showed that a hybrid strategy using Spacy Transformer BERT and Spacy Natural Language Processing (NLP) worked effectively for deriving information from CVs in the experimental dataset. Furthermore, it effectively recovered the names of applicants, contact details, qualifications, and previous jobs held together with other relevant details about the individuals concerned.

Alkeshwar et al., (2023) [17] recommended a model to enhance the hiring process by employing ML and NLP techniques to extract useful information from resumes so that they provide accurate ratings based on the company's requirements. According to the authors, after testing and refining it properly, this model's web portal could be a rich resource for both job seekers and employers. Another thing is the additional aspects such as personalized feedback and suggestions for improvement of resumes should be encompassed in for candidates to know what field they need to improve on before applying for the job vacancy.

Sreelasya et al., (2023) [18] emphasized the increasing competitive nature of the selection process in the corporate world, specifically through job fairs organized for college students targeting young talent. Initial screening was done by human resources using manual recruitment techniques based on resumes. The paper suggested deep learning for resume analysis to improve efficiency during recruitment processes.

Chavare et al., (2023) [19] considered an automated resume screening system using advanced NLP. This model performs quick and efficient resume screening by extracting relevant details from resumes using job descriptions. This system automatically recognized significant features from CVs when the Spacy NER Model was applied. Joint NER and relation extraction further improved information retrieval process through knowledge graphs, heading towards novel methods where various nodes could be explored to find hidden relationships. Therefore, this approach simplifies the overall process of recruitment, making it more user friendly.

Irfan et al., (2022) [20] Suggests that RCS (Resume Classification System) is appropriate by showing the effectiveness of nine machine learning classification methods such as Support Vector Machine - SVM (Linear, SGD, SVC and NuSVC), Naive Bayes (Bernoulli, Multinomial and Gaussian), K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) and Logistic Regression (LR). RCS did well using the Term-Frequency-Inverse-Document-Frequency (TF-IDF) method for representing features. For the evaluation, the Confusion Matrix, F-Score, Recall, Precision and overall Accuracy were used to check the accuracy of the methods. SVM from the family of one vs. rest classification strategy performed better than others with a 96% accuracy rate results obtained in this research for multi-class Resume classification task using about nine hundred sixty plus parsed resumes.

Anushka et al., (2022) [21] analysed that screening bulk of resumes is not a simple task for recruiters, which is time consuming and tedious. Typically, an organization handles hundreds or thousands of resumes, among them mostly consist of tangential information which are all in diverse formats and irrelevance too. If machine learning is used, a better and faster

selection process is created so recruiters do not need to examine each resume individually. KNN Algorithm helped place the resumes into appropriate groups. For recruiters, the model facilitates scanning the resume based on entered requirements they have specified.

Kinge et al., (2022) [22] noted that the rise of the Indian recruitment market in the past half-decade is due to the need for cheap labour rising with the rise in the number of open positions. Thus, when there is abundance of jobs available in different times – companies are formed whereby others outsource the hiring process itself but specialize solely in providing the right talent required for such companies. Therefore, even though they have established Talent Acquisition Companies that manually go through all resumes from candidates consume a lot of time, tediousness hence such kind businesses selectively use different Machine Learning algorithms streamline out the most relevant resumes for specific job roles; this lessens the HR team’s efforts.

Alessandro et al., (2022) [23] presented an effective end-to-end framework that derived personal information, skills, and work experience from resumes. The basic idea behind the system is to extract raw data from resumes into semantically equivalent chunks using linguistic patterns. It later on applies the Named Entity Recognition (NER) algorithm on pre-trained language-based models on every segment. Consequently, HR specialists can use this information when evaluating whether they have find the skilled applicant or not for the desired position. As an experiment, they came up with an Italian resume dataset with labels, which proves their approach worked well enough. Notably, the segmentation strategy increases NER performance compared to conventional line-based methods, while combined with modern NLP models, it demonstrates promising results.

Shestakova et al., (2022) [24] considered hybrid filtering as a method that can be used to improve recommendation quality by solving the cold jerk problem facing such systems today. This sort of problem came up when the system had no way to associate users with items due to lacking information. Skillset vectors might be a way to deal with data scarcity which is another challenge for recommender systems. The paper talked about how well Distil BERT and BERT models can be used in a career recommender system. A comparison was made between the online evaluation (user testing) results and those of traditional offline evaluations of the ML model’s quality.

Ranganath et al., (2022) [25] presented a smart recruitment system (SRS) with deep learning-based resume classification along with NLP techniques, automatic questionnaires’ that is set as a parameter to check the applicant technical proficiency assessed through syntactic similarity, where there were semantic similarities between two sentences or more, it could impeccably relate to the exact requirements required for a particular skill set. The author suggested named entity recognition to derive crucial data for the recruitment process using NLP. Regardless of the diverse format as a PDF or Word document, of the resume, the proposed method extracted applicant-associated data such as work experience and education. For simplifying and efficient recruitment process, parsing and ranking of resumes were made for.

3. Table: Comparison of existing work

Author	Year	Technique Used	Parameters
Lokesh. S, Mano Balaje. S, Prathish. E and B. Bharathi	2022	Machine Learning classifiers: Logistic Classifier Support Vector Machine Decision Tree Classifier	F1-0.72 F1-0.40 F1-0.52
Riya Pal, Shahrukh Shaikh	2022	Nave Bayes,	Accuracy 45%

		Random Forest SVM	70%, 60%
Aakankshu Rawat , Siddharth Malik,	2021	A combination of machine learning frameworks and existing DL based algorithms	Not specified
Dipti Suhas Chavare and Mrs. Archana Bhaskar Pati	2023	Spacy NER model	Not specified
Chirag Daryania, Gurneet Singh Chhabrab,	2020	Vector Space Model	Cosine similarity for ranking of resumes
Riza Tanaz Fareed, Rajath	2021	K-NN model	Accuracy-0.98%
Vedant Bhatia	2019	BERT model	Accuracy-72.77%
Irfan Ali 1a, NimraMughal 1b	2022	SVM, Naïve Bayes K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN), and Logistic Regression.	SVM classifiers performs better with Accuracy-98%
Gopalakrishna S.T., Vijayraghavan Mehran	2022	Named Entity Recognition (NER) approach coupled with Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbors	Efficiency of classifiers is determined
Bhoir, Nirmiti	2023	BERT, Deep learning model.	Accuracy 90%-92%

4. CONCLUSION

The concept of resume sorting and screening has been widely used in recruitment process and varied classification models have been built using machine learning techniques. Machine learning has become a powerful and transformative tool for providing the potential to revolutionize the process of automation of recruitment industry. With this automation, recruitment agencies can streamline their process of recruitment inclusive of factors such as cost-time optimization and choosing the skilled person for the right job. A good resume out of the bulk of resumes can be effectively and efficiently screened with the help of these trending machine learning techniques. Different Machine Learning methods provide an edge over the conventional models with characteristics including text classification, feature extraction, adaptability and semantic nuances. Future research should focus on addressing the challenges associated with these systems and trying to overcome the challenges faced in the literature work.

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